

1 **Temporal separation of tumor antigen induction during transformation *in vivo*.**

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6 The rapid kinetics of transformation occurring in experimental systems modeling genesis of cancer in
7 humans through tumor suppressor deletion or mutation complicates understanding of expression of genes
8 that specifically identify the onset of activity associated with transformation. A collection of genes could be
9 identified as marking cells with some level of sensitivity and specificity as having progressed into a
10 transformed state.

11 **Results**

12 The tumor antigens included genes of the CT, MAGE, XAGE, placental (PLAC), chorionic (CGB), testis
13 (TEX), and carcinoembryonic (CEACAM) families, and other transmembrane proteins expressed the cell
14 surface including those encoded by FAM, TTC, TMEM, and Gpr families.

15 Genes that marked the onset of transformation or transformed cells within a tissue containing a mixed
16 population of cells that had completed transformation proper could be distinguished into two categories:
17 those associated with cancer, the embryo or development but encoded on the X or Y chromosome, and
18 those that similarly described a transformed or neoplastic cell but were encoded on chromosomes 1-22.